

LINGUISTIC RESOURCES ON RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *The development of intelligence is closely related to the development of creative abilities. Understanding this, we do not mean the mechanical memorization of cultural studies information, but the manifestation of intellectual initiative in solving problematic and cognitive-exploratory cultural studies tasks, participating in cultural studies discussions, and creating group and individual cultural studies projects.*

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Higher education institutions play a significant role in enhancing intercultural cooperation. Currently, there are positive trends in the development of intercultural competence among students. The modernization of higher education concepts allows for the combination of various training courses, resulting in a more flexible education system. This system includes general courses, advanced courses, and elective courses. Achieving a high level of intercultural competence in students is essential for their successful integration into the complex network of cultural relations in today's world.

The main difference lies in the fact that students' educational activities require significant intellectual engagement and independence. Our experience in teaching Russian language demonstrates that introducing students to a new educational experience is a complex process. Many students encounter difficulties in learning Russian because they have not fully developed the cognitive aspects of intercultural competence.

To master the program material in depth, it is necessary to develop generalizing, conceptual thinking at a sufficiently high level. Difficulties that students often face in the learning process are not primarily related to their inability to learn in new conditions, but rather to their reluctance to learn. According to N. E. Golovanova, Yu. B. Kuzmenkova, P. V. Sisoyev, the attitude of students to study gradually begins when they understand the need to master Russian language and culture. If we talk about the direction of youth thinking, we can say that it is related to formal logical operations and specific features of the emotional world of early youth. The mental activity of students is characterized by a high level of generalization and abstraction, a tendency to explain phenomena causally, to argue with opinions, the ability to prove the truth or falsity of individual rules, and critical thinking. All these are necessary conditions for forming theoretical thinking, understanding the general laws of the surrounding world, the laws of nature, and society development. In the elective course "Intercultural Education of Students", students learn to compare and classify Uzbek, Russian, and English cultures, find common and specific features of the presented linguistic information, and also represent their country in the world.

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but the manifestation of intellectual initiative in solving problematic and cognitive-exploratory cultural studies tasks, participating in cultural studies discussions, and creating group and individual cultural studies projects.

As a methodological basis for the development of students' intercultural competence, we identified L.S. Vygotsky's cultural-historical concept, which in our study implies comparative work with linguistic and cultural materials to master the forms and methods developed historically by students.

According to V.V. Safonova, the idea of cultural communication is a methodological principle and should be based on the pedagogical level itself. According to the scientist, "Teaching Russian communication in the context of the dialogue of cultures includes the creation of didactic and methodological conditions for the comparative humanistic-oriented joint study of Russian language and Uzbek culture in the development of integrative communication skills of intercultural dialogue. In addition, the methodological advantage makes students participants or subjects of the dialogue of cultures. It should be oriented towards formation.

Intercultural education can be implemented when students have the opportunity to understand and compare the knowledge they have acquired about Uzbek and Russian culture at the same time and to connect their experience with others. The role of the text in teaching Russian culture is incomparable. V.V. Chernyshev emphasizes that the perception and creation of live speech is a reliable means of developing and strengthening the linguistic sense.

According to V. I. Chernyshev, an important idea from the point of view of the studied problem is that the meaning of reading should not be limited to only one understanding of what is being read, because full development requires not only the perception of thought but also its mastery. At the same time, conveying what has been read orally and in writing is one of the means of strengthening ideas.

Linguistic resources mean didactic tools (graphic texts, audio, and video data), which include three levels:

- cognitive (resources for mastering a set of knowledge that allows a systematic understanding of cultural reality);
- communicative (resources for mastering the rules of speech and non-verbal behavior in the context of Russian language);
- valuable (resources containing educational tools for understanding the traditions, norms, and values of another culture).

Thus, linguistic resources represent knowledge about the studied culture, and accepted norms of behavior and are characterized by the following features: practical orientation, representation by socio-cultural, functional-stylistic and correlational, monologue and dialogic speech samples. Based on linguistic resources, by analyzing and interpreting them, students learn the norms and possibilities of constructing different sentences from Russian language. Linguistic resources in the environment of the studied culture are a good opportunity to expand the socio-cultural and linguistic space and ensure communication in it.

The educational nature of teaching is manifested in the selection of the content of the educational process and didactic organization: The experience of pedagogical research in recent years proves the possibility of the existence of a real pedagogical practice that shows the connection between the educational and upbringing processes (Sh.A.Amonashvili, V.V.Davidov,

and others). We defined the linguistic and cultural criteria for educational materials for the development of intercultural competence of students of higher education institutions:

- adaptation of linguistic resources to educational opportunities, interests, and needs of students;
- high theoretical and practical value of materials, their educational and developmental value;
- theory of didactic unity of substantive and procedural aspects of teaching content;
- Inclusion of functionally adequate culturally oriented texts in the content of the "Intercultural Education" course.

Based on the theory of text activity in the lingua-social-psychological context (T.M. Dridze), by working with linguistic resources, we can exchange an active oral dialogue in the process of searching, comparing, further critical analysis and purposeful use of the cultural and socio-psychological context. Two interrelated types of reading can be used to work with graphic materials - exploratory and critical. In this regard, medium-sized binary texts and accompanying text tasks are adopted to develop skills related to understanding their content. Working with bilingual resources, therefore, means understanding the manifestation of another culture, whose artistic and aesthetic system is specially organized, to find culturally valuable information that allows access to the deep semantic layers of the main cultural concepts.

Working with linguistic resources in higher education depends on three factors: the student's problematic life situation; the communicative and cognitive skills of the student; and strategies chosen by students to compare cultural phenomena.

Foreign scholars approach the definition of intercultural competence from a behavioral point of view and identify several behavioral qualities of a person that constitute competence in communicating with representatives of other cultures. Among these qualities, the following stand out:

- giving respect and positive assessment to another person;
- biased positive attitude towards the behavior of another person;
- the ability to accept the point of view of the interlocutor, to look at the event from his position;
- ability to tolerate unexpected turns of events.

In the works of W.J. Pruegger and T.B. Rogers on intercultural education, it is emphasized that developing intercultural competence should focus on enhancing students' communication skills when interacting with individuals from other cultures. Additionally, this process should involve regulating and managing behavior. Foreign researchers H.N. Seele, R.M. Paige, and J.N. Martin assert that developing intercultural competence also fosters specific personality traits essential for effective interactions with people from diverse cultural backgrounds. Five main conditions contribute to the development of intercultural competence:

- 1) respect differences in cultures;
- 2) development of cultural reflexive ability;
- 3) to be aware of the dynamics of cultural interaction, which are mutually opposite (ethnocentrism + ethnorelativism),
- 4) institutionalization of cultural knowledge;
- 5) develop adaptive skills to understand the differences between cultures and within cultures themselves.

K. Knapp identifies the following components of intercultural competence:

- knowledge of communicative actions and their interpretation in one's own and the culture being studied, as well as in Russian language;
- General knowledge of the relationship between culture and communication, including the dependence of thinking and behavioral styles on cultural characteristics of thinking, as well as the differences between cultures determined by these characteristics;
- a set of strategies for stabilizing interaction, i.e. solving problems that arise in the process of communication

Analyzing various definitions of intercultural competence and its content, we conclude that the quality under study is a set of personal qualities (decency, cognitive activity, attention to the effectiveness of intercultural communication, ability to learn), knowledge of system values and relationships (knowledge of cultural values and the features of communication with representatives of other cultures), contribution to the formation of value-semantic, cognitive, emotional-volitional and behavioral results (i.e., the ability to perceive, understand and explain the phenomena of other cultures and the ability to compare them with the values of the local mentality and national traditions, find commonalities and differences, critically understand them and integrate them into one's image).

In turn, we identify three components of intercultural competence: cognitive, emotional-evaluative, and communicative-active. The level of intercultural competence is determined by the formation of all its components, the interconnection of which allows you to establish positive relationships with representatives of other cultures. The development of intercultural competence is a long and dynamic process of personal development aimed at harmonizing two or more socio-cultural worlds in the student's mind, understanding their similarities and differences, and recognizing the interaction of linguistic and cultural variables in people's actions.

The study of theoretical literature has revealed a broad trend in the development of research on the problem of intercultural interaction and the problem of raising an intercultural person: identifying new aspects of analysis and searching for effective methods of developing the phenomenon under study.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva S.N. Communicative approach to the formation of spelling competence in teaching the Russian language in Uzbek groups of the Academic Lyceum: Ped. Science. Fal. Doc. diss. ... author's abstract – Tashkent
2. Aliyev M.Ch. Methods of teaching Russian language using computers in national groups of non-linguistic universities: Abstract of diss. ... candidate of ped. Sciences. – Tashkent, 1991.
3. Belozeroва A.A. Intercultural foreign language teaching and education of linguistic students (based on the German language). Diss. Cand. Ped. Sciences. - Yekaterinburg, 2018
4. Vasilyeva H.H. Intercultural competence. Strategies and techniques for achieving it. Electronic resource. URL: <http://rspu.edu.ru/journals/lexicography/conference/vasilieva%20N.htm> (date of access: 18.02.2022)
5. Maslova V.A. Linguistic culture. Fly away. posobie dlya stud. Higher fly deluded. - M.: center "Academy", 2011,
6. Jinkin N.I. Yazyk. Rech. Creativity. - M.: 1998.

7. 5. Larin B.A. Istoriya russkogo zazyka i obshchee yazykoznanie (Izbrannye raboty). - M.: 1977, -P.175-190
8. Baldwin J.R., Coleman R.R.M., González A. Intercultural communication for everyday life. Somerset, GB: Wiley-Blackwell; 2013.